

Visual Banking, A Modern Techno Dynamism in Smart Phone Banking– A Research on Innovative Banking Technologies in Chennai

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Abstract

Techno dynamism has made tremendous changes in the life style of human beings. Banking is no exception to this. Stormy techno dynamism has been going on in banking technological innovations, since 1990s. Traditional Brick and Desk banking (Branch banking) was replaced by Digital Banking since 1990s. Digital Banking has been more popular since 2014 due to the talk of "Digital India". Mobile banking is a part of Digital banking. Gone are the days when people trusted on trunk dialing (before 1990s). Mobile phones were converted into smart phones (since 2010s) and such smart phones have been part and parcel of almost all the people, just like 6th finger of palm in our hand. People have been using Smart phones for multiple purposes, such as phone calling, internet usage and so on. Since internet is embedded in mobile phone, this facilitates mobile banking smoothly and quickly. Year 2016, after demonetization (November 8, 2016) forced most of the people to go for Digital banking. Paytm and Mobikwik, Airtel money, Jio money were becoming more popular and people started using mobile banking since then. Video Banking is a new dimension in mobile banking. This is known as Visual Banking. Very few banks have been following this Video banking, by having a special app. Without app, the customers have to talk to the bank officials by video conferencing method. Some customers have been using mobile banking have been using Video banking (125 customers out of 600). They are mostly corporate customers and few of them are professionals and home makers. This Video conferencing method of banking helps the bank customers to talk to the bankers as if they are seeing them in person. Therefore, personalized attention is possible, integrated with virtual presence. The non-users of Video banking (475 out of 600) are also interested to use Video banking very shortly. This innovation has been going on at infancy level since 2016 in various banks. Therefore, it will pick up at speed here in after. Video banking will be a boon to the future generation, both for bankers and customers. Integration of Robots for banking is mostly wanted by customers, by and large. Interactive Teller machines (ITMs) for withdrawal of money are yet another welcoming technology, due to the advent of Video banking. Customers have been using Video banking for bank transactions clarification, documents verification and confirmation, Digital signature confirmation and so on. In near future, Video banking will be flickering its wings at greater speed and start flying at greater heights. Robot banking will also

be more popular here in after. Time will come very soon, by integrating all the banking technologies namely, Digital banking, Mobile banking, Robot Banking together, in the name of Collaborative banking (C Banking), to facilitate individualized attention to customers, mass customization, virtual presence and agility in offering banking services. Time is not so far away in this regard, since we are all living in the era of Techno dynamism. This article brings forth the research data related to mobile banking and video banking.

Keywords: Visual Banking, Video banking, Agility banking, Just in time banking, Corporate Banking, Retail Banking, Digital Banking, Virtual Banking, Robot banking, Smart Watches Banking, Smart Phone Banking, i-way banking, Sky banking, SMS banking.

Introduction

Mobile banking has been popular since 2010s, after the advent of internet embedded smart phones, and it has been more popular after demonetization on November 8, 2018. Paytm, petty payment through mobile has been understood by the customers by force, since then. Like these services, several banks came out with various mobile banking apps for launching the same in their banking. SBI, ICICI Bank, HDFC Bank have brought several apps for mobile banking. Technological dynamism has brought video banking. There is a company namely Vidyo. This company has been providing a specialized software for facilitating Video banking software. In India, some banks started to implement Video banking. Video banking can be done by using apps or video conferencing by using the mobile numbers of bank employees. In near future, several people will use video banking and this will become more popular. Mobile banking is the baby of Digital banking. Mobile banking has given birth to Video banking. If mother jumps for 8 feet, baby will jump for 16 feet. Just like this verse, mobile banking and video banking have been becoming more popular among the people, particularly the initiating people who are techno dynamism addicts. Techno dynamism addicts are the people who are the initiators of accepting technological innovation arrivals and they accustom to use the same. They are the first-time learners and they would teach it to others, in their peer team.

Visual Banking

Visual banking means doing banking transactions by interacting with the bank officers online, by having either video banking apps or by having video conferencing method. This brings individualized attention to the customers, with virtual reality.

Recent Technological Advancements on Mobile Banking (As of Now)

The following are the recent technological advancements that are in existence as of now.

- a) Mobile banking
- b) SMS Banking for checking balance enquiry
- c) SMS Banking by using quick codes or SMS codes or Key words
- d) Interactive Voice mechanisms
- e) Banking transactions by using Smart phones – Usage of Apps for doing such banking transactions
- f) Video Banking
- g) Smart watches banking

Future Emerging Technological Advancements

The following are the emerging technological innovations that will happen very soon in near future and far future.

1. Mobile Banking and Digital banking advancements
2. Block chain technology

3. Smart watches
4. Google glasses
5. Upgraded ATMs, ATMs in the name of ITMs (Interactive Teller Machines) for doing multiple banking functions
6. Automated Financial services
7. Strategic partnerships
8. Extended Application Interfaces
9. Artificial Intelligence in Apps and Online banking transactions
10. Extended Security measures by using biometrics and video mechanisms and ensuring higher level security mechanisms
11. Video banking and Extended virtual reality
12. Robot banking
13. Application of Internet of things in retail banking
14. Focus on Retail banking and personalization of banking services
15. Cloud computing technologies and Sky banking

Review of Related Literature

There are various researches on Digital banking and a few researches on Smart banking are available. The researchers reviewed 72 such literatures. Among all, there is only one research article on Video banking and this is the main thing for the present research. An article captioned, “Video banking, a new dimension in Mobile banking”, by Saravana Kumaran, et al, published in Journal of Emerging technologies in innovative research, published in November 2018 was analysed and reviewed. In that research, the periodicity was 2016 – 2018. The present research is made in 2018 – 19, recently. In the previous research, only few respondents were the users of video banking (25 users only). Whereas, the awareness and usage on video banking has been increased within in this one year. In the present research, the users of video banking are 125. The usage rate has been increased. As the usage is getting increased, the expectations on improvements are also getting increased. Therefore, comparing to the previous research made by Saravana Kumaran, et al, in 2018, this present research brings forth better research results.

Research Methodology

This research article has been prepared to meet out a couple of objectives. First, to understand the usage level and satisfactory level of mobile banking and offer suggestions for its improvements. Second, to know the usage level and satisfactory level of video banking from the users and offer suggestions for its improvement from the users and non-users.

The research has been made in Chennai. Primary data have been collected during the year 2018 – 2019. Whereas the previous research was conducted by Saravana Kumaran, et al, in 2016 – 18. But the present research has been conducted in 2018 – 19, recently.

Multi Stage Quota Sampling method has been followed. For the purpose of sampling, technologically advanced banks were selected, based upon best technological banking award ceremony, 2015 (Table 1 and 2). There are 16 banks available who are the Best technological banking award winners under 9 categories of technological advancements. The banks such as SBI, UBI, IDBI Bank, PNB, IOB, Corporation Bank, Central Bank of India, Bank of India, Andhra Bank are the Best technological banking award winners among Public Sector banks. HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, Indus Ind Bank, Karnataka Bank and South Indian Bank are the Best technological banking award winners among Private Sector Banks category. Citi Bank is there under Foreign Bank category (1 bank). Out of 16 banks, only Indian Banks were considered, i.e.,

15 Indian banks were selected for sampling purpose (94%). Citi bank is a foreign bank. Therefore, it was not considered. Hence, 9 Public Sector banks and 6 Private Sector banks were selected for the research (Totally 15). From such banks, 40 customers from each bank were contacted for collecting primary data. Among such 15 banks, 40 customers for each bank, totally 600 customers were contacted. Only the customers who have been using Digital Banking technologies were contacted for the purpose of this Research. Non users of Digital Banking were not considered. In order to know the technological adoption of Digital Banking practices, only the users can say the correct information. Therefore, they were alone contacted. By considering Law of inertia and Law of Statistical regularity, the sample size of 600 customers were selected by following Multi Stage Quota Sampling method. Such 600 customers were selected as follows.

After collecting the data, by using SPSS, Kaizer Meyer Olkin Measure method (KMO) of sampling adequacy is considered and it is 0.877. This means that sampling is adequate.

Regarding validity, Cronbach's Alpha has been analysed and this is 0.706, for the sample of 600 respondents. This conveys that the data are valid.

The sampling plan is as follows.

Public Sector Bank customers: $9 \text{ Banks} * 40 \text{ customers} = 360 \text{ customers}$

Such 9 banks are SBI, UBI, IDBI BANK, PNB, IOB, Corporation Bank, Central Bank of India, Bank of India and Andhra Bank (Uniformly 40 customers were selected from each bank)

Private Sector Bank customers: $6 \text{ Banks} * 40 \text{ customers} = 240 \text{ customers}$

Such 6 banks are HDFC Bank, ICICI Bank, Axis Bank, Indus Ind Bank, Karnataka Bank and South Indian Bank (Uniformly 40 customers were selected from each bank)

Such 600 customers were contacted, by bifurcating Corporate Banking customers (300) and Retail Banking customers (300 customers).

Corporate Banking customers (300 customers):

Manufacturers=100 customers

Traders / Shop keepers =100 customers

Service Business=100 customers:

Retail Banking customers (300 customers):

Independent Professionals=100 customers

Employees=100 customers

Students & Home makers=100 customers

Totally 786 customers were contacted and filtered into 600 for this research purpose. The respondents were contacted in person. Apart from such source, google forms were used and sent to the customers' email ids and whatsapp. The responses were collected and organised. Due care has been taken by the Researcher to avoid or minimize various errors namely, sampling error, Data errors, Statistical errors (Type I error and Type II errors).

Among such 15 banks, 10 branches were selected (15 banks * 10 branches in Chennai = 150 bank officers). Such bank branches were selected for contacting bank managers or officers or appropriate authorities to know technological banking adoption practices and innovations to be launched soon. This sample size of 150 has been selected by following Law of inertia and Law of Statistical Regularity. Such banking surveys are not included in this research article. But such survey details will be brought in another article in future.

In this research article, responses of customers are brought forth and presented. A research on Visual Banking, a modern techno dynamism in smart phone banking has been made and some of the results are portrayed in this article.

Regarding statistical calculations, manual analysis, analysis by using SPSS, analysis by using Excel are all made. Due care has been made to portray the statistical results correctly. Statistical

tests like Likert Scaling technique (5-point scale), Kruskal Wallis rank test, Spearman’s rank correlation, Wilcoxon signed rank test are applied suitably, after validating data.

There are a few limitations. Only Digital banking users are contacted and non-users are not considered. Time is yet another constraint. Chennai area (In and around Chennai) is the only area coverage. The periodicity is 2018 – 19. The responses are psychological in nature, subject to change when technological advancements happen and prosperities do happen. The responses may also change in future.

Table 1 - Best Banker Award in Launching Smart Banking Initiatives

S.No.	Criteria of Award	Public Sector Bank			Private Sector Bank / Foreign bank in India		
		Winner	First Runner up	Second Runner up	Winner	First Runner up	Second Runner up
1	Technology Bank of the year	SBI	IDBI Bank Ltd	Union Bank of India	HDFC Bank	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank
2	Best Internet Bank	SBI	Union Bank	IDBI Bank Ltd	HDFC Bank	ICICI Bank	Axis Bank
3	Best use of Business Intelligence	SBI	IOB	IDBI Bank Ltd	ICICI Bank	Citi Bank	HDFC Bank
4	Best Customer Management Initiatives	SBI	Punjab National Bank	Andhra Bank	HDFC Bank	Citi Bank	Karnataka Bank
5	Best use of technology intraining and e- learning	SBI	Union Bank	Punjab National Bank	ICICI Bank	HDFC Bank	IndusInd Bank
6	Best Risk Management and Security initiative	Punjab National Bank	Union Bank of India	IDBI Bank	ICICI Bank	HDFC Bank	Axis Bank
7	Best Financial Inclusion initiative	SBI	Bank of India	Central Bank of India	ICICI Bank	HDFC Bank	Axis Bank
8	Best use of mobility technology in Banking	SBI	Union Bank of India	Corporation Bank	HDFC / ICICI Banks	NA	Citi Bank
9	Best Payments initiative	Union Bank of India	IDBI Bank Ltd	SBI	ICICI Bank	Citi Bank	South Indian Bank

Source: Ernst & Young Global Limited, London, United Kingdom. Award Ceremony – 2015

Note: Since the primary data were collected in 2016 – 18, Best Banker Award 2015 was considered.

Table 2 - Pioneering Banks in Launching Smart Banking Initiatives

S. No.	Name of the Bank	Number of Awards	Rank	Public Sector / Private Sector
1	STATE Bank of India	8	I	Public Sector
2	HDFC Bank	8	I	Private Sector
3	ICICI Bank	8	I	Private Sector
4	Union Bank of India	6	II	Public Sector

5	IDBI Bank Ltd	5	III	Public Sector
6	Axis Bank	4	IV	Private Sector
7	Citi Bank	4	IV	Foreign bank
8	Punjab National Bank	3	V	Public Sector
9	Indian Overseas Bank	1	VI	Public Sector
10	Corporation Bank	1	VI	Public Sector
11	Central Bank of India	1	VI	Public Sector
12	Bank of India	1	VI	Public Sector
13	Andhra Bank	1	VI	Public Sector
14	IndusInd Bank	1	VI	Private Sector
15	Karnataka Bank	1	VI	Private Sector
16	South Indian Bank	1	VI	Private Sector
Total Awards		54		

Source: Ernst & Young Global Limited, London, United Kingdom. Award Ceremony – 2015

Note: Since the primary data were collected in 2016 – 18, Best Banker Award 2015 was considered. Among such 16 banks, 15 Indian banks were selected for the research.

Mobile Banking

Mobile banking has been more popular among corporate customers rather than retail banking customers. The research results are portrayed in the following table. Mobile banking has been classified into 7 categories, namely, SMS banking, Call banking, Online banking through Smart phones, Banking through Communication server providers, Petty payments through mobiles, Video Conference banking, Smart watch banking. There are certain sub classifications. The research results are pooled up in the following table.

Hypothesis: The Corporate banking customers and Retail Banking customers have been using mobile banking services equally well. The data are distributed uniformly.

Table 3 Usage of Mobile Banking Services

Mobile banking services	Usage of services					Total Yes	Total No	Total Weightage	Rank	Weightage Corporate	Weightage Retail	Mean
	VF	F	O	R	VR							
SMS Banking												
Getting SMS alert as and when any banking-transaction happens	587	11	2	NIL	NIL	600	Nil	2985	1	1488	1497	4.98

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Doing banking transactions by sending quicker codes by SMS	311	99	77	64	49	600	Nil	2359	6	1478	881	3.93
Call Banking												
Balance Checking, by giving missed call	523	31	28	10	8	600	Nil	2851	2	1400	14501	4.75
Satisfactory survey participation by giving missed call	316	88	36	32	128	600	Nil	2232	7	1384	848	3.72
Online Banking by Smart Phones												
Doing online banking transactions by Smart phones via bank apps	219	87	86	48	160	600	Nil	1957	8	1112	845	3.26
Online banking by mobile, by going to bank websites	318	191	37	54	Nil	600	Nil	2573	4	1462	1111	4.29
Banking through Communication Service Provider												
Banking via Jio money or Airtel money	379	98	66	37	22	600	Nil	2573	3	1461	1113	4.29
Petty Payments through Mobile												
Making payments through Paytm or Mobikwik	388	88	55	42	27	600	Nil	2568	5	1463	1105	4.28
Video Conference Banking												
Video Conferencing and banking transactions by smart phones	80	30	15	Nil	Nil	125	475	565	9	501	64	4.52

Video Conferencing by laptops or desktop computers	78	28	14	10	1	125	475	545	10	497	48	4.36
Banking through Smart Watches												
Doing banking through smart watches	Nil	18	4	3	Nil	25	575	90	11	90	Nil	3.60

Note: Weightage points: Very Frequently = 5 points; Frequently = 4 points; Occasionally = 3 points; Rarely = 2

points; Very Rarely = 1 point

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

Spearman's Rank Correlation (based on weightages of corporate banking and retail banking) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n2(n-1))] = R = +0.53381 = +0.53$ (approx.)

Medium level positive degree of correlation

Please note: Video banking and Smart watches banking details are related to corporate banking only. Therefore, when correlating corporate banking and retail banking, such details were not considered.

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.18262.

Therefore, Relationship is very weak, based on p value.

In the case of unpaired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 118.5$; $\sum R2 = 71.5$; H value is 0.4926; p value is 0.48; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56 Calculated value of H is 0.4926 < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis. Therefore, it is inferred that the data have been distributed uniformly.

In the case of unpaired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Mann Whitney's U test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 118.5$; $\sum R2 = 71.5$; U value is 35.5; Table value of U = 31; Table Value of U1 < Calculated value of U. Reject Hypothesis.

Therefore, Corporate customers and Retail Banking customers do usage of mobile banking services, but their usage level is different. Corporate customers have been using mobile banking more than retail banking customers.

Z value is 0.66058; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56

Calculated value of U is 0.66058 < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis. Therefore, it is inferred that the data have been distributed uniformly.

It is inferred from the above table that Corporate Banking customers have been using mobile banking services mostly well, rather than retail banking customers. In the case of SMS banking, missed call banking only, retail banking customers have been using them more. Video banking and Smart watches banking have been performed only by corporate customers for their business purposes. Statistical tests like U test and KS test prove that the data have been uniformly distributed. U test reveals that corporate customers have been using mobile banking services more than retail

banking customers. Rank Correlation between Corporate banking and Retail banking on the usage of mobile banking services reveals that they are correlated positively at medium level (0.52).

Satisfaction of Mobile Banking Services

The following table brings forth the information on satisfaction of mobile banking services. Hypothesis: The Corporate banking customers and Retail Banking customers are satisfied with mobile banking services equally well. The data are distributed uniformly.

Table 4 – Satisfaction of Mobile Banking Services

Mobile banking services	Usage of services					Total Yes	Total No	Total Weightage	Rank	Weightage Corporate	Weightage Retail	Mean
	HS	S	Neu	DS	HDS							
SMS Banking												
Getting SMS alert as and when any banking transaction happens	594	6	Nil	Nil	Nil	600	Nil	2994	1	1599	1495	4.99
Doing banking transactions by sending quicker codes by SMS	317	100	82	54	45	600	Nil	2392	6	1480	912	3.99
Call Banking												
Balance Checking, by giving missed call	527	39	32	2	Nil	600	Nil	2891	2	1405	1486	4.82
Satisfactory survey participation by giving missed call	321	93	45	33	108	600	Nil	2286	7	1395	891	3.81
Online Banking by Smart Phones												
Doing online banking transactions by Smart phones via bank apps	223	91	90	52	144	600	Nil	1997	8	1117	880	3.33
Online banking by mobile, by going to bank websites	321	191	88	Nil	Nil	600	Nil	2633	5	1477	1156	4.38
Banking Through Communication Service Provider												
Banking via Jio money or Airtel money	403	101	67	27	2	600	Nil	2676	4	1483	1193	4.46
Petty Payments Through Mobile												
Making payments through Paytm or Mobikwik	405	105	80	10	Nil	600	Nil	2705	4	1485	1220	4.51
Video Conference Banking												
Video Conferencing and banking transactions by smart phones	82	28	14	1	Nil	125	475	566	10	502	64	4.53

Video Conferencing by laptops or desktop computers	74	26	16	9	Nil	125	475	550	9	498	52	4.40
Banking Through Smart Watches												
Doing banking though smart watches	18	7	Nil	Nil	Nil	25	575	118	11	118	Nil	4.72

Source: Primary data

Note: Weightage points: HS – Highly satisfied = 5; S – Satisfied = 5; Neu – Neutrally satisfied = 3; DS – Dissatisfied = 2; HDS– Highly dissatisfied = 1

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

Spearman’s Rank Correlation (based on weightages of corporate banking and retail banking) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n_2 (n- 1))] = R = +0.7381 = + 0.74$ (approx.) High level positive degree of correlation Please note: Video banking and Smart watches banking details are related to corporate banking only. Therefore, when correlating corporate banking and retail banking, such details were not considered.

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.03655.

Therefore, Relationship is moderate, based on p value.

In the case of unpaired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R_1 = 113; \sum R_2 = 77; H$ value is 0.0614; p value is 0.80; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of H is $0.0614 < \text{Table value of acceptance region } 2.56$. Accept hypothesis In the case of unpaired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Mann Whitney’s U test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R_1 = 113; \sum R_2 = 77; U$ value is 41; Table value of U = 31; Table Value of $U_1 < \text{Calculated value of U}$. Reject Hypothesis.

Therefore, Corporate customers and Retail Banking customers get satisfaction on mobile banking services, but their satisfactory level is different. Corporate customers have been satisfied with mobile banking more than retail banking customers.

Z value is 0.20643; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56

Calculated value of U is $0.20643 < \text{Table value of acceptance region } 2.56$. Accept hypothesis

It is inferred from the above table that Corporate Banking customers have been satisfied with mobile banking services mostly well, rather than retail banking customers. Video banking and Smart watches banking have been performed only by corporate customers for their business purposes. They are satisfied with such services. Statistical tests like U test and KS test prove that the data have been uniformly distributed. U test reveals that corporate customers have been satisfied with mobile banking services more than retail banking customers. Rank Correlation between Corporate banking and Retail banking on the usage of mobile banking services reveals that they are correlated positively at high level (0.74).

Relationship Between Usage and Satisfaction on Mobile Banking Services

From Table number 3 and 4, correlation was made between the usage and satisfaction on mobile services. The results are as follows.

Hypothesis: The usage level and satisfactory level on mobile banking services are correlated

positively among the Corporate banking customers and Retail Banking customers at equal level. The data are distributed uniformly.

Spearman's Rank Correlation (based on total weightages of usage and satisfactory level) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n2 (n-1))] = R = +0.95578 = +0.96$ (approx.) Higher level positive degree of correlation
Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.00001.

Therefore, Relationship is very strong, based on p value.

In the case of paired data, we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on total weightages of usage level and satisfactory level). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 117; \sum R2 = 136; H$ value is 0.3891;

p value is 0.53; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of H is 0.3891 < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis

In the case of paired data, we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on total weightages of usage level and satisfactory level for corporate banking and retail banking = totally 4 criteria). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 213.5; \sum R2 = 129; H$ value is 1.1928; p value is 0.75; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of H is 1.1928 < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis

In the case of paired data (based on total weightages of usage level and satisfactory level), we can apply Mann Whitney's U test (based on total weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 117; \sum R2 = 136; U$ value is 51; Table value of U = 31; Table Value of U1 < Calculated value of U. Reject Hypothesis.

Therefore, Corporate customers and Retail Banking customers get satisfaction on mobile banking services, but their satisfactory level is different. Corporate customers have been using mobile banking and they are highly satisfied with mobile banking more than retail banking customers.

Z value is 0.593; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of U is 0.59 < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis

In the case of paired data (usage level and satisfactory level), we can apply Wilcoxon Signed Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 117; \sum R2 = 136; W$ value is 0; Z value is 2.43; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of 2.43 is < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis

It is inferred from table 3 and 4 that Corporate Banking customers have been using mobile banking services and they have been satisfied with such services mostly well, rather than retail banking customers. Video banking and Smart watches banking have been performed only by corporate customers for their business purposes. They are satisfied with such services. SMS Banking and Call banking have been used by Retail banking customers more and they are satisfied well. Statistical tests like U test, Wilcoxon signed rank test and KS test prove that the data have been uniformly distributed. U test reveals that corporate customers have been satisfied with mobile banking services more than retail banking customers. Rank Correlation between Corporate banking and Retail banking on the usage of mobile banking services reveals that they are correlated positively at higher level (0.96).

Benefits Enjoyed on Mobile Banking Services

The customers have been enjoying various mobile banking services. The research results are pooled up in the following table. Agility banking or Just in time banking is possible because of mobile banking.

Hypothesis: Corporate customers and retail banking customers have been enjoying mobile banking services equally well. The data are distributed uniformly.

Table 5 Benefits on Mobile Banking Services Enjoyed by the Customers

Mobile banking services	Satisfactory attitude					Total	Weightage points	Mean	Rank	Weightage Corporate	Weightage Retail
	HS	S	Neu	DS	HDS						
Arrival of SMS as and when transactions happen help us to know balance amount correctly	580	18	2	Nil	Nil	600	2978	4.96	1	1499	1481
Online banking transactions by using smart phones ease banking activities	448	83	69	Nil	Nil	600	2779	4.63	5	1399	1380
Doing banking transactions becomes easy due to mobile banking by SMS	227	185	97	67	22	600	2330	3.88	6	1176	1156
Balance Checking by giving missed call	527	35	38	Nil	Nil	600	2889	4.82	4	1464	1425
Missed call for dissatisfaction registration	531	39	30	Nil	Nil	600	2901	4.83	3	1433	1468
Agility banking – Just in time banking	519	64	17	Nil	Nil	600	2902	4.84	2	1420	1382

Source: Primary data

Note: Weightage points: HS – Highly satisfied = 5; S – Satisfied = 5; Neu – Neutrally satisfied = 3; DS – Dissatisfied = 2; HDS– Highly dissatisfied = 1

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

Spearman’s Rank Correlation (based on weightages) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n^2 (n-1))]$ = R = +0.93286 = + 0.93 (approx.) Higher level positive degree of correlation

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.0048.

Therefore, Relationship is very strong, based on p value.

In the case of paired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Wilcoxon Signed Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 42$; $\sum R2 = 36$; W value is 4; Z value is 1.3628; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56 Calculated value of 1.3628 is < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis

In the case of paired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 42$; $\sum R2 = 36$; H value is 0.2308; p value is 0.63; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of H is 0.2308 < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis.

SMS alert makes the customers to know the balance amount in their account as and when transaction happens (Rank 1). Agility banking is possible (Rank 2). Missed call for dissatisfaction makes the customers to express their feelings immediately (Rank 3). Missed call for balance

checking eases bank transactions (Rank 4). Further, it is learned by applying various statistical tests such as KS test, Wilcoxon Signed Rank test that data are distributed normally. Both corporate customers and retail banking customers have been enjoying the benefits of mobile banking equally well. The relationship between them is higher level positive degree (0.93).

Common Problems of Mobile Banking Services

The customers have been suffering from some problems on mobile banking services. Such research results are pooled up in the following table.

Hypothesis: Corporate customers and retail banking customers have been suffering from problems on mobile banking services equally. The data are distributed uniformly.

Table 6 - Common Problems of Mobile Banking Services Felt by the Customers

Mobile banking services	Satisfactory attitude					Total Yes	Total No	Weightage points	Mean	Rank	Weightage Corporate	Weightage Retail
	HF	F	Neu	LF	VLF							
Frequent SMSes disturb unnecessarily	317	87	37	31	128	600	Nil	2234	3.72	5	1132	1102
Poor network problem	418	84	38	34	26	600	Nil	2634	4.39	2	1334	1300
SMS locking may be done by any hacker secretly	389	86	57	41	27	600	Nil	2569	4.28	3	1354	1212
While using Smart phones for banking transactions, double entry or problem happens due to network issues	523	32	29	9	8	600	Nil	2848	4.75	1	1438	1410
Account hacking threat by hacker	378	77	66	52	27	600	Nil	2527	4.21	4	1314	1213
Loss of smart phone and misuse of bank account	38	10	8	3	1	60	540	261	4.35	8	137	224
Theft of smart phone and misuse of bank account	40	12	5	2	1	60	540	268	4.47	6	138	230
Strangers identify pattern or password of smart phone, take it and misuse it	38	15	3	3	1	60	540	266	4.43	7	136	230

Source: Primary data

Note: HF – Highly felt; F – Felt; Neu – Neutrally felt; LF – Least felt; VLF – Very least felt
 Weightage points: HF – Highly felt= 5; F – Felt = 4; Neu – Neutrally felt = 3; LF – Least felt = 2; VLF – Very least felt = 1

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

Spearman’s Rank Correlation (based on weightages) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n^2 (n-1))] = R = +0.91573 = + 0.92$ (approx). Higher level positive degree of correlation

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.0014.

Therefore, Relationship is very strong, based on p value.

In the case of paired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Wilcoxon Signed Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 69$; $\sum R2 = 67$; W value is 15; Z value is 0.42; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56
 Calculated value of 0.42 is < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis.

In the case of paired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 69; \sum R2 = 67; H$ value is 0.011; p value is 0.91; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56
Calculated value of H is $0.011 < \text{Table value of acceptance region } 2.56$. Accept hypothesis

It is observed from the above table that double entry may happen because of network issues (Rank 1), followed by poor network problems (Rank 2), SMS locking may be done by strangers (Rank 3), Account hacking issues (Rank 4) and disturbances due to SMS unnecessarily (Rank 5). Some of the customers (40 customers out of 600) suffered a lot due to loss of their smart phone, misuse of their smart phone by strangers, loss of amount from their account due to abuse of their smart phones. It is analysed from KS test, Wilcoxon Signed Rank test that the data are distributed normally. Both corporate customers and retail banking customers have been suffering from problems on mobile banking equally. The relationship by Rank Correlation expresses that they are related very strongly at higher level of positive degree (0.92).

Improvement of Mobile Banking Services

Improvements are the continuous processes. Several improvements were suggested by customers on mobile banking development. They are brought to the following table.

SMS Banking

Regarding SMS banking, SMS locking by strangers must be informed to alternative mobile number of customers. Like this suggestion, several suggestions are made by the customers. They are pooled up in the following table.

Hypothesis: Corporate customers and retail banking customers have been offering suggestions for the improvement on SMS banking equally well. The data are distributed uniformly.

Table 7 Attitude on Improvement Expected in SMS Banking Services Suggested by the Customers

Mobile banking services	Satisfactory attitude					Total	Weightage points	Mean	Rank	Weightage Corporate	Weightage Retail
	MNP	NP	Neu	O	LN						
In the case of savings bank account, SMS on balance has to come as and when transaction happens	523	41	36	Nil	Nil	600	2887	4.812	2	1401	1486
In the case of current account, SMS has to come once in a day (say 9 pm daily)	317	87	36	32	128	600	2233	3.722	10	1433	800
SMS locking aspect (by hacker) has to be informed to the banker or alternative mobile of customer immediately	525	43	32	Nil	Nil	600	2893	4.722	1	1487	1406
Loss or theft of ATM card or credit card has to be informed by SMS to the banker by a special quick code	419	99	82	Nil	Nil	600	2737	4.562	5	1431	1306

In the case of RD and FD, the aggregate amount till date has to be informed by SMS once in a month (end of the month)	421	99	82	Nil	Nil	600	2737	4.562	4	1432	1307
In the case of loan account, the net balance payable has to be informed as and when transaction happens	317	187	96	Nil	Nil	600	2621	3.368	6	1422	1199
SMS regarding loan payment reminder is needed, before one week of due date	423	97	80	Nil	Nil	600	2743	4.572	3	1423	1320
Insurance premium deduction has to be informed to the customer one week before, in order to maintain sufficient balance	320	184	73	23	Nil	600	2601	4.335	7	1400	1201
Cheque dishonor & bill dishonor details have to be informed to the customer as and when happens	285	161	84	36	34	600	2427	4.045	8	1429	1998
All the banks must have quick codes in SMS banking. This eases mobile banking	327	97	56	42	78	600	2353	3.922	9	1273	1080

Source: Primary data

Note: Weightage points: MNP – Most Necessary and top priority = 5; N – Necessary and moderate priority = 4; Neu – Neutrally necessary (moderately) = 3; O – Optional = 2; LN – Least necessary = 1

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

Spearman’s Rank Correlation (based on weightages) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n^2 (n-1))]$ = R = +0.16464 = + 0.16 (approx.). Lower level positive degree of correlation

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.6494.

Therefore, Relationship is very weak, based on p value.

In the case of paired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Wilcoxon Signed Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 129.5; \sum R2 = 80.5; W$ value is 11; Z value is 1.6818; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of 1.6818 is < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis.

In the case of paired data (Corporate banking and Retail Banking), we can apply Kruskal Wallis Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 129.5; \sum R2 = 80.5; H$ value is 3.43; p value is 0.0642; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.05$ is 3.52. Calculated value of H is 3.43 < Table value of acceptance region 3.52. Accept hypothesis

SMS locking or hacking has to be informed by SMS to an alternative mobile number of the customer (Rank 1). Instant SMS for SB account, Account summary SMS at the end of the day for Current account (Rank 2) will be enough instead of having frequent SMSes that are horrible. SMS

regarding payment reminder is essential to make necessary arrangement in business (Rank 3). It is learned by applying various statistical tests namely KS test, Wilcoxon Signed Rank test that the data are distributed normally. Corporate customers have been offering more suggestions (because of more usage) rather than retail banking customers. The relationship between suggestions offered by corporate customers and retail banking customers is lower positive degree (0.16).

Online Banking by using Smart Phones

Online banking transactions can be done either through bank apps or bank websites, by using Smart phones. The suggestions on the improvement of such services are listed in the following table.

Table 8 Attitude On Improvement Expected In Online Banking By Smart Phones Suggested By The Customers

Mobile banking services	Satisfactory attitude					Total	Weightage points	Mean	Rank
	MNP	NP	Neu	O	LN				
Integration of Video Conferencing with bank officials (Video banking)	425	81	54	33	7	600	2690	4.483	3
Security strength is needed in mobile banking by modern technologies	429	85	56	23	7	600	2706	4.510	2
Banker has to conduct meetings with customers atleast once in 3 months to teach technological upgradations done by the banker	317	98	65	42	78	600	2334	3.890	7
Banker has to resolve mobile banking problems intime	327	97	56	42	78	600	2353	3.922	6
All the banks need to have satisfactory surveys byhaving missed call	285	167	90	34	24	600	2455	4.092	4
Specialised apps need to be developed by all the banks and to be launched at the earliest	515	55	30	Nil	Nil	600	2885	4.808	1
Need for computer integrated voice by using toll free number for each and every bank	275	157	80	54	34	600	2385	3.975	5

Source: Primary data

Note: Weightage points: MNP – Most Necessary and top priority = 5; N – Necessary and moderate priority = 4; Neu – Neutrally necessary (moderately) = 3; O – Optional = 2; LN – Least necessary = 1

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

All the banks need to create special apps for mobile banking (Rank 1). Information Security is the major necessity (Rank 2), followed by Video banking necessity (Rank 3).

Video Banking

The corporate customers (125 out of 600) have been using video conferencing with the bank officials for accelerating their bank transactions and to do their bank transactions fairly well. The following table tells what modes are being utilized by the corporate customers for video banking.

Table 9 - Mode of Usage of Video Banking Services

Video banking services modes	Usage of services					Total	Weightage points	Mean	Rank
	VF	F	O	R	VR				
Smart phone	83	23	19	Nil	Nil	125	564	4.512	1
Tabs	38	37	26	13	11	125	453	3.624	4
Laptops	82	22	21	Nil	Nil	125	561	4.488	2
Desktop computers	56	34	23	Nil	Nil	125	485	3.880	3

Source: Primary data

Note 2: Weightage points: VF -Very Frequently = 5 points; F - Frequently = 4 points; O - Occasionally = 3 points; R - Rarely = 2 points; VR – Very Rarely = 1 point

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

It is understood from the above table that corporate customers have been using Smart phones for video banking (Rank 1), followed by Laptops (Rank 2), Desktop computers at their offices or homes (Rank 3) and Tabs (Rank 4). Smart phones and Laptops are the major modes used by the corporate customers for video banking.

Usage of Video Banking Services and Satisfactory Level

The usages of video banking services are pooled up in the following table.

Hypothesis: The usage level and satisfactory level of video banking services are equal. The data are distributed uniformly.

Table 10 Usage and Satisfactory Level of Video Banking Services

Video banking services	Usage of services					Total	W1	Rank	Satisfaction on services						W2	Rank
	VF	F	O	R	VR				HS	S	Neu	DS	HDS	Total		
Bank transaction clarification	124	1	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	624	1	123	2	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	623	1
Digital signature approval and confirmation	121	3	1	Nil	Nil	125	620	3	120	4	1	Nil	Nil	125	619	3
Bearer cheque confirmation	111	6	5	3	Nil	125	600	5	112	8	7	Nil	Nil	125	613	5
Bill of exchange clarification and confirmation	35	35	26	15	14	125	437	7	116	6	3	Nil	Nil	125	613	6
Loans obtaining and settlement clarification	36	35	25	14	15	125	438	6	110	9	6	Nil	Nil	125	604	8
Documents verification over	122	2	1	Nil	Nil	125	621	2	122	2	1	Nil	Nil	125	621	2
Online banking problems - solutions	118	4	3	Nil	Nil	125	615	4	120	3	2	Nil	Nil	125	618	4
Complaints lodging and solutions	34	33	23	14	11	125	410	8	116	4	3	2	Nil	125	609	7

Source: Primary data

Note: Percentages are available in brackets

Note 2: Weightage points: VF -Very Frequently = 5 points; F - Frequently = 4 points; O - Occasionally = 3 points; R - Rarely = 2 points; VR – Very Rarely = 1 point

Spearman’s Rank Correlation (based on weightages) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n^2 (n-1))] = R = +0.9102 = + 0.91$ (approx.). Higher level positive degree of correlation

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.00169.

Therefore, Relationship is strong, based on p value.

In the case of paired data, we can apply Wilcoxon Signed Rank test (based on weightages). By applying this test, we find, $\sum R1 = 60.5$; $\sum R2 = 75.5$; W value is 3; Z value is 1.85; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of 1.85 is < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis.

Corporate customers have been using Video banking facility, mainly for clarification of bank transactions (Rank 1), followed by documents verification over phone (Rank 2), Digital signature approval confirmation (Rank 3), online banking problems and solutions with bank employees (Rank 4) and complaints lodging and solutions (Rank 5). The data are distributed normally, by analyzing by Wilcoxon test. The relationship between the usage level and satisfactory level are correlated positively, strongly at higher level positive degree (0.91). Both usage level and satisfactory level are at equal level.

Common Problems on Video Banking

Corporate customers have been facing some problems on video banking commonly. They are brought up in the following table.

Table 11 Common Problems on Video Banking Services Faced by the Customers

Video banking services	Satisfactory attitude					Total	Weightage points	Mean	Rank
	HF	F	Neu	LF	VLF				
Light background issues	118	3	2	1	1	125	611	4.888	6
Colour, hue and pixels issues	114	4	3	2	2	125	601	4.808	8
Mobile software compatibility issues	112	6	5	1	1	125	602	4.816	7
Pass word security issues	123	1	1	Nil	Nil	125	622	4.976	2
Hacking problems	121	3	1	Nil	Nil	125	620	4.960	4
Blue tooth issues – nearby strangers would receive our video clippings	123	1	1	Nil	Nil	125	622	4.976	3
Loss of smart phones may be misused for mishandling bank account	121	2	2	Nil	Nil	125	619	4.952	5
Network issues	124	1	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	624	4.992	1

Source: Primary data

Note 1: R1 – Rank 1; R2 – Rank 2; W1 – Weightage for users; W2 – Weightage for non-users

Note 2: HF – Highly felt; F – Felt; Neu – Neutrally felt; LF – Least felt; VLF – Very least felt
Weightage points: HF – Highly felt = 5; F – Felt = 4; Neu – Neutrally felt = 3; LF – Least felt = 2; VLF – Very least felt = 1

Please Note: Mean here refers to an average. This is calculated on total weightage points / Number of respondents who told positively for the particular question.

It is observed from the above table that network issues are the major worries (Rank 1), followed by pass word security issues (Rank 2), Blue tooth issues (Rank 3), Hacking issues (Rank 4), loss of smart phone fear issues (Rank 5).

Possible Improvements on Video Banking

Corporate users who have been using Video banking answered the possible improvements on Video Banking. Besides, non-users of Video banking (but users of Digital Banking) have also answered this question. The following table portrays the necessary data.

Hypothesis: The improvements on Video banking expected by users and non-users are at equal level. The data are distributed uniformly.

**Table 12 Improvements Expected In Video Banking
(by regular users and non-users, but users of digital banking)**

Video banking services/usages	Regular users					Tot	W1	R1	Non users, but users of Digitalbanking						W2	R2
	MNP	NP	Neu	O	LN				MNP	NP	Neu	O	LN	Tot		
24/7 Video Banking service	120	2	2	1	Nil	125	616	5	442	15	14	3	1	475	2319	6
Usage of Robots for banking transactions, for video conferencing	119	3	2	1	Nil	125	615	6	458	7	5	4	1	475	2342	5
Interactive Teller Machines need to come (Video conferencing ATMs)	125	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	625	1	470	4	1	Nil	Nil	475	2369	1
Capturing overseas customers and having banking transactions	118	3	2	2	Nil	125	612	7	331	49	32	24	39	475	2334	8
Specialised apps are needed for videobanking separately	124	1	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	624	2	469	2	2	1	1	475	2362	2
Video conferencing may be recorded for documentation purpose– Paperless documentation	36	36	26	25	2	125	454	8	341	38	32	34	30	475	2051	7
Offline mode has to be created to avoid-network issues	123	2	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	623	3	461	5	4	3	2	475	2345	4
User friendly smart phone software’s need to be developed to avoid mobile system compatibility issues	122	3	Nil	Nil	Nil	125	622	4	462	5	4	3	1	475	2349	3

Source: Primary data

Note 1: R1 – Rank 1; R2 – Rank 2; W1 – Weightage for users; W2 – Weightage for non-users

Note 2: Weightage points: MNP – Most Necessary and top priority = 5 Points; N – Necessary and moderate priority = 4 Points; Neu – Neutrally necessary (moderately) = 3 points; O – Optional = 2 points; LN – Least necessary = 1 point

Spearman’s Rank Correlation (based on ranks) = $[1 - (6\sum d^2 / n2 (n-1))] = R = +0.92357 = +0.92$ (approx.). Higher level positive degree of correlation.

Two tailed p value for rank correlation = 0.00086.

Therefore, Relationship is very strong, based on p value.

In the case of paired data, we can apply Wilcoxon Signed Rank test (based on ranks). By applying this test, we find,

$\sum R1 = 68; \sum R2 = 68; W$ value is 10.5; Z value is 0.001; Acceptance region of z at $\alpha = 0.01$ is 2.56. Calculated value of 0.001 is < Table value of acceptance region 2.56. Accept hypothesis

It is learned from the above table that the users and non-users want to have Interactive Teller Machines (ITMs), improved version of ATMs (Rank 1). Such ITMs would capture the videos of

persons who use ITMs and we can interact with the machines for withdrawing money or making deposits with the money. This will be a boon to all, particularly to computer illiterates. Specialized apps are needed for Video Banking (Rank 2). All banks need to develop such apps compulsorily. Offline support system is needed (Rank 3). User friendly phone software's are needed (Rank 4). Any time (24/7) Video banking services with the help of Automated computerized Robots will facilitate the customers more delighted (Rank 5). Wilcoxon test proves that the data are distributed normally. The suggestions of users and non-users are equally made. The relationship between the improvements suggested by the users and non-users are correlated positively at higher positive degree (0.92). This shows that non users are also willing to invite Video banking whole heartedly.

Conclusion

Digital Banking has given birth to mobile banking. If mother jumps for 8 feet, child jumps for 16 feet. Mobile banking has been more popular among various bank customers. Similarly, Mobile banking delivers a baby called Video banking. This infant will jump more than 100 feet probably in near future. Future banking will be Robot Banking. Robots started its functioning in City Union Bank, T. Nagar, Chennai and ICICI Bank, Bangalore, since 2016. Video banking integrated with Robot banking will become more popular here in after. Therefore, so far ignored personalized attention will be taken into consideration and integrated with virtual presence. Collaborative banking will come very soon, by integrating, Digital banking, Mobile banking, Video banking, Robot banking together. Time may come very soon to have Tsunamic techno dynamism in banking technologies. People are ready to welcome the new technologies here in after also.

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